

Instructions for depositing data in Tilburg University Dataverse

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1 Introduction

This document offers a **guide to deposit data packages or other research data in Tilburg University Dataverse (TiU Dataverse)**, the official Tilburg University (TiU) data repository for long term storage. TiU Dataverse is part of **DataverseNL**, a data repository platform used by several Dutch universities and managed by the national organization Data Archiving and Networked Services (**DANS**). DataverseNL is built upon a scientific platform developed by Harvard University and is used worldwide. More information about TiU Dataverse can be found on the [General information about TiU Dataverse](#) page.

Before depositing research data in TiU Dataverse, **researchers should make sure that:**

- They have permission to share the files (i.e., the files are free of third-party rights, copyrights, and other legal limitations to share).
- They considered which license and/or terms of use are appropriate for the research data they want to deposit.
- The **files** are in a **format**¹ that guarantees the best long-term usability² when possible.
- They have anonymized or pseudonymized³ any eventual privacy-**sensitive information**.
- No individual file they want to deposit exceeds 9.3 GB in size⁴

For questions, researchers can contact the TiU Dataverse Curators of the Research Data Office (dataverse@tilburguniversity.edu).

2 Deposit research data in TiU Dataverse

The steps below explain how to deposit research data in TiU Dataverse.

2.1 Log in to DataverseNL

1. Go to <https://dataverse.nl>
2. Click LOGIN in the upper right corner (see Figure 1):
3. Click Institutional login (see Figure 2):
4. Select Tilburg University as institution (see Figure 3)

Dataverse Terms of Use

When you log in to DataverseNL for the first time, you have to give permission to send your information to DataverseNL and accept the [terms of use](#).

2.2 Go to your department's collection

DataverseNL is organized in collections. Most Dutch universities have their own DataverseNL collection. TiU Dataverse is one such collection. TiU Dataverse itself is further organized in five collections, one for each Tilburg University school. Each school collection is then subdivided into collections for each department within the school. When you

deposit your research data, you should deposit it in your department's collection. To reach your department's collection follow these steps:

1. Go to the TiU Dataverse [landing page](#);
2. **Click on the name of your school** (see Figure 4), which will bring you to the TiU Dataverse school landing page;
3. **Click on the name of your department** (see Figure 5)

2.3 Create a new data record

1. Click Add Data⁵ (see Figure 6)
2. Select New dataset

2.4 Fill in the metadata

Some metadata fields are already filled in for you. Fields indicated with an asterisk are mandatory. We encourage you to fill in as many fields as possible because this will make your research data easier to find and understand by others. Hover over the question marks if you need some more information about any metadata field.

2.5 Upload your data files

1. Click on the button + Select Files to Add at the bottom of the page (see Figure 7).
2. Select files to be uploaded to the TiU Dataverse data record from your computer

 Tip: Maintain folder structure

To maintain the folder structure when uploading a data package, the entire folder must be added as a zip file. Once the data package is uploaded, you can verify that the structure has been preserved by clicking the button 'Tree' under the tab 'Files' (Figure 8). If you want to upload a zip archive and not have Dataverse unzip it, you must double zip the folder.

2.6 Save the data record as a draft

Click the button Save Dataset at the bottom of the page (see Figure 9).

 Tip: The Draft Status

As long as your data record is in a draft status, it is possible to add more files and metadata by clicking the **'Edit dataset'** button.

2.7 (Optional) Restrict access to files

1. In the **Files** tab of your data record, click on the three vertical dots on the right of a file you want to restrict;
2. Click **restrict** (see Figure 10);
3. Write custom terms of access for this file (for more information see [here](#)). Any user who wants to download the restricted file will have to meet any requirement you list here to get access and use the data.

Access requests

By default, a restricted file will allow access requests. Access requests are automatically sent to the TiU Dataverse Curators who will then contact you to ask your permission to grant or deny access to your data. When your contact email address is no longer in use (for example after your employment with TiU ends), the university's policy is to ask the head of your department to grant or deny access. You can also disable access requests if access to the file should not be granted under any circumstance (see Figure 11).

2.8 Check the Dataset Terms

By default, TiU Dataverse assigns CC0 (Creative Commons zero) to every data record, which means that researchers place their work in the public domain, so that others can reuse and build upon this work for any purposes without restrictions. The Dataset Terms will not apply to files with restricted access.

To change the dataset terms:

1. Click on the **Terms** tab of your data record
2. Click at **Edit Terms Requirements** (see Figure 12):
3. Select a different license from the dropdown menu (see Figure 13)

You can choose one of the predefined Creative Commons Licenses, or custom terms. To stimulate open science as much as possible, **TiU recommends to apply CC0 or the CC BY license**. For more information on data licenses and data use agreements, see the Table 1 or the [Data licenses Tilburg University page](#).

Table 1: Creative Commons Licenses

License	Can I copy & redistribute the work?	Is it required to attribute the author?	Can I use the work commercially?	Am I allowed to adapt the work?	Can I change the license when redistributing?
CC0	Y	N	Y	Y	Y
CC BY	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
CC BY-SA	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
CC BY-ND	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
CC BY-NC	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
CC BY-NC-SA	Y	Y	N	Y	N
CC BY-NC-ND	Y	Y	N	N	Y

2.9 Submit the data record for review

When you save your data record, it has the `draft` status and it is not published yet. As long as your data record is still a `draft`, you can make changes. When you are satisfied, click the button `Submit for review` in the right upper corner (see Figure 14). The TiU Dataverse Curators will check the quality of the data record to ensure that the data and documentation meet the requirements of the [CoreTrustSeal](#).

3 Publication procedures

3.1 First publication

Once you have submitted the data record for review, the following steps will take place:

1. **Data check**—Two TiU Dataverse Curators will check whether the data, documentation, and metadata meet the requirements of the [CoreTrustSeal](#). If the data record does not meet the requirements, you will be contacted by email to discuss possible changes.
2. **Data publication**—When the data record meets the requirements, it will be published. Once your data record is published by the TiU Dataverse Curators, it can be found by other users. You can use the persistent URL (DOI) to refer to your data record, for example in a publication.
3. **Notification on completion**—You will receive an automatic email confirming the data record has been published.

3.2 Updating a published data record

You can update a published data record in TiU Dataverse by editing files or metadata as needed. After making changes, click ‘Submit for review.’ A TiU Dataverse Curator will review your submission, and once approved, a new version of your dataset will be created while retaining the same DOI. Previous versions remain accessible under the `Versions` tab.

3.3 Deaccessioning a published data record

Once your data record is published, it is not possible to delete it. A data record can be deaccessioned (i.e., made no longer visible) by the TiU Dataverse Curators in special cases. When a data record is deaccessioned its files are no longer visible and the DOI will lead to a tombstone page.

4 Advanced functionalities

4.1 Use of embargoes

TiU Dataverse allows researchers to set embargoes on individual files when creating or editing a dataset. An embargo temporarily restricts access to selected files until a specified end date. Once a file has been published, it can no longer be embargoed.

To set an embargo:

1. Select files for which you want to set the same embargo period.
2. Click `Edit files`.
3. Click `Embargo`.
4. Choose an end date using the calendar.
5. Provide a reason for the embargo.
6. Click `Save Changes`.

When the embargo end date is reached, the file automatically becomes accessible under the specified terms. If you need to change an embargo end date after publication, please contact the TiU Dataverse Curators at dataverse@tilburguniversity.edu.

4.2 Sharing without publishing the data record

Researchers can share access to an unpublished dataset (draft) using one of the following features:

- **Private URL**—A Private URL allows access to a dataset draft without requiring a DataverseNL account. To generate a Private URL:
 1. Click `Edit` in the dataset page.
 2. Select `Private URL`.
 3. Click `Create Private URL` and share the link. Anyone with this link can view and download the dataset.
- **URL for anonymized access**—A URL for Anonymized Access allows dataset access without displaying certain metadata fields, including:
 - Author
 - Dataset Contact
 - Contributor
 - Depositor
 - Grant Number
 - Related Publication
 - Distributor
 - Producer

Important: Anonymization applies only to these metadata fields. Other dataset elements, **including the Dataverse name** (i.e., the school and department name), remain visible.

- **Granting access to other DataverseNL users**—If the recipient has a DataverseNL account, you can assign them specific permissions instead of sharing a Private URL:
 1. Go to `Edit > Permissions > Dataset`.
 2. Click `Assign roles to Users/Groups`.
 3. Select the user and assign access rights.

Note: The user must have logged in at least once to DataverseNL to be assigned a role. This is also possible for external users who cannot use SURFconext; they can create a local DataverseNL account instead.

4.3 Using HTML in Metadata Fields

TiU Dataverse supports [these HTML tags](#) in certain metadata fields, such as the Description field. This allows researchers to improve readability by adding bullet points, changing the formatting of text (e.g., bold, italics). For example:

- To make text bold researchers can use the HTML tag ``:

```
This <b>word<\b> is bold
```

will render as

“This **word** is bold”

- To add an hyperlink researchers can use the HTML tag `<a>`:

```
Please see this <a href="https://www.tilburguniversity.edu">page</a>
```

will render as

“Please see this [page](#)”

4.4 Connections with external platforms

Researchers can connect other repositories they use to Dataverse to simplify the upload of files and other aspects of creating a data record on DataverseNL.

- **Open Science Framework (OSF)**—Linking OSF with TiU Dataverse allows researchers to view, download, and upload files between the two platforms. Please see [OSF instructions](#) for more information.
- **GitHub**—Using the [Dataverse Github integration](#), researchers can connect GitHub to Dataverse to upload files from a GitHub repository to an existing Dataverse data record. As of version 1.6, researchers should keep in mind that the integration has the following limitations:
 - The integration does not allow to create a new Dataverse dataset from a GitHub repository.
 - The integration does not allow to modify metadata of the Dataverse dataset based on metadata provided in the GitHub repository.
 - The integration does not currently support submission for review (see GitHub Issue [Add submit for review option under Publish](#))
- **API**—The Dataverse Software APIs allow users to write their own integrations with external platforms. For more information see the official Dataverse [guide](#).

Notes

1. [TiU file formats information](#)
2. See the [list of preferred formats](#) for more information on the preferred file formats for TiU Dataverse.
3. See the TiU [page](#) on anonymization and pseudonymization for more information.

4. If your file size exceeds this limit, please contact the [TiU Dataverse Curators](#) to learn about other possibilities for data deposit.
5. If you do not see the button Add Data, check that you are logged in.

Screenshots

Figure 1: Click Log in to log in to Dataverse NL

Figure 2: Click Log in with Your institution

Figure 3: Select Tilburg University as institution

Figure 4: Click the name of your school

Tilburg School of Social and Behavioral Sciences
 (Tilburg University)

DataverseNL > Tilburg University >

Welcome to the Tilburg University Dataverse! To create a new dataset, **please follow the next steps:**

1. Access the **Dataverse of your department** or, otherwise, go to step 2:
 - o Department of Social Psychology
 - o Tranzo
 - o Department of Methodology and Statistics
 - o Department of Medical and Clinical Psychology / CoRPS
 - o Department of Human Resource Studies
 - o Developmental Psychology
 - o Department of Cognitive Neuropsychology
 - o Department of Sociology
 - o Department of Organization Studies
2. Click the **+ Add Data** drop-down menu and select **New Dataset**
3. Fill in the form that pops up. For further guidance, you can [use this guide](#)

*You need to log in to see this menu

Questions? Please contact dataverse@tilburguniversity.edu

Figure 5: Click the name of your department

Department of Methodology and Statistics
 (Tilburg University)

DataverseNL > Tilburg University > Tilburg School of Social and Behavioral Sciences >

[Advanced Search](#)

- 1 New Dataverse
- 2 New Dataset

Dataverses (0)
 Datasets (14)
 Files (1,194)

Publication Year
 2024 (2)
 2023 (2)
 2022 (4)
 2018 (1)
 2017 (2)

1 to 10 of 14 Results

Statistical Modeling Techniques for the Analysis of Relational Event Networks
 Jun 26, 2024
 Generoso Vieira, Fábio, 2024, "Statistical Modeling Techniques for the Analysis of Relational Event Networks", <https://doi.org/10.34894/D1YZJQ>, DataverseNL, V1
 This is the code used for the experiments and simulations in the PhD dissertation: Statistical Modeling Techniques for the Analysis of Relational Event Networks. The main purpose is to assess methods to develop methods and models to analyse relational event networks.

Replication Data for: Simplifying Imputation with Many Predictors in MICE Using Principal Component Analysis
 May 7, 2024

Figure 6: Create a new data record

Figure 7: Select files to upload

Figure 8: Check the folder structure in tree view

Figure 9: Save the data record

Figure 10: Restrict access to a file

Figure 11: Enable or disable access requests

Figure 12: Edit terms

Figure 13: Choose other terms

Figure 14: Submit for review